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Integrated education model of information technology and accounting: A new approach to accounting education

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Abstract

Accounting Education requires attention for the development of cross-cutting knowledge. It is paramount to change the traditional paradigm of education, for developing such knowledge or cross-cutting competencies among the student this paper will analyze the various research evidence available under different teaching pedagogies, the role of technology, and the 4-dimensional integrated model in education & virtual environments. This paper also pinpoints various challenges and opportunities in accounting education under virtualisation and suggests possible solutions for facilitating the change and integration of technology based virtual learning environments to improve the teaching learning process.

Keywords: Accounting education, traditional paradigm, teaching pedagogies, virtual learning

Introduction

According to Late Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam, "Education is the most important element for the growth and prosperity of a nation". So, every country tries to develop an education system that will help the nation to achieve both economic and social objectives. The growth of technology and infrastructure has created a different form of education i.e. virtual education. It uses technological and other information communication networks to conduct teaching and learning processes. "A virtual learning environment (VLE) is a set of teaching and learning tools designed to enhance a student's learning experience by including computers and the internet in the learning process". With the help of VLE, students can sit in front of the screen of their computer, tablet, mobile, and laptop and acquire the knowledge delivered by their teachers. The components of VLE are breaking curriculum into sections, student tracking, online support for both teacher and student, electronic communication, and internet links. MOOCs will prove the quality of accounting education and the knowledge level of students (Ambadkar *et al.* 2015) [2]. Virtual learning environments have not added any value to the students' accounting knowledge level (Love & Fry 2006) [26]. Broad *et al.* (2004) [9] focused on the adoption of technology in an accounting course and they mentioned that students found it more interesting. The present study attempts to explore different opportunities and challenges in virtual education and the possible solutions to overcome the challenges.

Research Evidence

Traditional teaching methods

Cullen *et al.* (2004) [12] discovered that case studies had a positive impact on students' research abilities. The aforementioned conclusions are supported by Weil *et al.* (2004) [36], Hwang *et al.* (2005) [21], and Braun and Simpson (2004) [8]. According to Nouri and Shahid (2005) [29], using PowerPoint to instruct students enhances their performance. According to Arquero-Montano *et al.* (2004) [4], traditional teaching techniques have no impact on students' academic performance. The aforementioned conclusions were corroborated by Hosal-Akman and Sigma-Mugan (2010) [20] and Clinton & Kohlmeier (2005) [10].

Contemporary teaching methods

Gujarathi (2005) [17] illustrated how ERP software affects students' motivation for studying accounting. According to Marriott (2004) [27-28], the use of simulation games in accounting education improves students' learning and critical thinking skills.

The above findings were supported by Hoffjan (2005) as well as Green and Calderon (2005) [16].

Web-based education

According to Lindquist and Olsen (2007) [25], studying online enhances students' ability to solve accounting-related problems. The findings above were corroborated by Peng (2009) [31] as well as Kopel and Dudley (2003) [23]. However, Abdolmohammadi *et al.* (2003) [1] depicted that the internet did not improve the understanding level of students.

Distance Teaching Methods

According to Tirovouzis (2006) [38], virtual teaching has a good impact on students' performance. The aforementioned conclusions are supported by Stanley and Edwards (2005) [34], Dunbar (2004) [15], Sidiropoulos (2008) [32], and Koukoufiki (2009) [24]. According to Marriott *et al.* (2004) [27-28] and Wells *et al.* (2008) [37], students have a preference for both traditional and online teaching. Virtual teaching, according to Halabi *et al.* (2002) [19], Halabi (2005) [18], and

Basioudis and De Lange (2009) [16], has no effect on students' performance.

Hybrid Systems

The hybrid model has a good impact on students' performance, according to research by Dowling *et al.* (2003) [14]. The aforementioned conclusions are supported by Barsky and Catanach (2005) [5] and Spathis (2004) [33]. Internships have been shown to improve student proficiency, according to Anderson and Bauman (2004) [3] and Still and Clayton (2004) [35].

Integrated Model in Education

“The proposed model (with a working title Model of integration of virtualization into the education – IVE) operates with three basic dimensions and one integrating dimension, defines the scope of activity of virtualization technology when used as a means for teaching about virtualization and simultaneously as a means for teaching with virtualization” (Klement, 2016) [22].

Fig 1: Klement's model of integration of virtualization in education

a) School's Infrastructure

This dimension deals with the use of technology and virtualisation at schools for their activities and operations. It exclusively is concerned with the internal technological operations of the schools. This dimension includes servers' virtualising for economic, accounting, administrative, operational, and other activities & services; infrastructural virtualisation; etc.

b) Teaching regarding Virtualization

The focus of 2nd dimension is the inclusion of technology of virtualisation in the course content and curriculum. It makes the pupils and students aware of the practical operation and administration of virtual technology under a given situational setup. The activities of administration, operation, and configuration of virtual technology and its elements are covered under this aspect of the model.

c) Teaching with Virtualisation

The use of virtual technology for the teaching learning process is what this third dimension of the model deals with. Teaching with virtual technology works in line with the previous dimension of teaching about

virtualisation, not in isolation. The teaching-learning process in a virtual environment has to be supported with infrastructural and other technological aspects as well. The reproduction of applications and software for educational purposes, installation and configuration of hardware and software and operating systems, testing of systems, etc are the activities and parts of this dimension.

d) Integration

The final dimension of the proposed model is regarding the integration of the 3 basic dimensions into one. The scope of the dimension covers starting from the school-level infrastructure and technology, implementation of virtual technology in the system, and subject content till the use of virtual technology in the teaching-learning process. Operationalization of virtual technology in classrooms, data centers, and within the teaching-learning frameworks, etc are the major activities of the integrating dimension of the proposed model.

Teaching Learning Pedagogy for Accounting Education

Table 1: Traditional vs Modern Pedagogy

Basis	Traditional pedagogy	Modern pedagogy
Teaching	Teachers use chalk, blackboard, whiteboard, and Marker in traditional teaching.	Teachers use smart boards, and power points in modern teaching.
Examinations	Examinations are conducted in offline mode or classroom examination	Examinations are conducted in online mode through online tests or on the online platform
Question and Answer	In traditional mode, question and doubt clear sessions are done through face to face.	In modern pedagogy, students used to email or test the doubts or questions.
Course Material	Students use books, notes, and reports under traditional mode.	Students use e-books, journals, and blogs in modern mode.
Accounting Education	Usually, students use a calculator, pen, pencil, and copies for solving accounting problems.	Students use MS Excel and other accounting software for solving accounting problems.
Assignment	Students deposit an assignment in a physical copy.	Students deposit an assignment in soft copy.
Group Assignments	In traditional mode, group assignments can be done by sitting in a classroom.	In modern mode, it can be done through spreadsheets and Google documents.

Source: Self Compiled

Opportunities for Virtual Education

a) Students

The content can be downloaded and read at the students' convenience. They can also become more adept at time management, absorb and apply information in accordance with their learning capacities, and become self-regulated learners by using hypermedia and user-friendly documents. By getting over the problem of geographic limitations, online learning can provide students with additional alternative possibilities. Students who are uncomfortable asking questions in class because they are shy or embarrassed can feel more at ease in a virtual learning environment. Additionally, students will have the chance to work together with peers and educators from all across the world.

b) Teachers

By employing electronic documents, educators can save time, enhance the quality of their instruction, reach a wider range of students, and acquire experience with web-based tools and technology.

c) Institutions

A wider range of students may be accessed through virtual education, which will also improve reputation and recognition and aid in the development of a worldwide online community. It aids in cutting expenses.

Challenges of Virtual Education

a) Students

Face-to-face support, student demotivation, and quality assurance issues were all decreased by the virtual learning environment. In order to comprehend shared information more effectively and efficiently, students need to be tech-savvy, able to handle technology and other online networks, have communication skills, and be able to interact virtually with others through the use of electronic technology. They also need to be somewhat independent.

b) Teachers

The faculty will spend more time for preparing the online content and it leads to an additional workload.

c) Institutions

E-learning systems need a number of things, such as course administration systems, enough bandwidth, technologically advanced classrooms which is costly. Faculty resistance and more personnel are needed by the institutions.

Possible Solutions to Overcome the Challenges

It is necessary to design student-friendly software, give computer education to all students, and encourage students to take advantage of virtual learning. Market-oriented accounting courses should be made available, an integration accounting model should be implemented, and the infrastructure for virtual accounting education should be built. The government must offer financial support for the establishment of virtual learning in every institution, and faculty members must receive training in online content preparation and online evaluation.

Conclusion

Enhanced use of virtual environment and technology in the teaching methods in the present accounting education are considered to be repetitive and obsolete, and results in dissatisfaction of both teachers and students, thereby recognizing the significance of promoting enhanced student participation and involvement. Recently, nationally and internationally, there have been distance learning programs (e-learning), in semi-face-to-face systems (e-blended learning) and integrated into the face-to-face teaching-learning process. This is because the need for a change in the traditional teacher-student roles has become evident, where teachers have been considered as designers, managers & evaluators of the training process through exposure to the knowledge, and students reproduce their knowledge as passive spectators of the class. In short, promoting the active participation of students without neglecting the relevance of books to multimedia means, that is, taking the best of each modality (face-to-face and virtual).

In this modern era, traditional education can be replaced with new teaching pedagogical methods which help both students and teachers in the teaching-learning process. "The proposed model (with a working title Model of integration of virtualization into the education – IVE) operates with three basic dimensions and one integrating dimension, defines the scope of activity of virtualization technology when used as a means for teaching about virtualization and simultaneously as a means for teaching with virtualization" (Klement M., 2016) ^[22].

The available opportunities and prospects of a virtual technological environment can benefit the existing Accounting educational system in India, provided the quality of the course and its content is guaranteed. The practicals associated with the teaching-learning process of accounting subjects like e-accounting and e-filing etc, can be very conveniently handled by imparting training and

awareness. The virtual learning environment may not be a cure for all existing issues in imparting accounting education in India. Exploiting the virtual technology, for imparting accounting education may still be at its infancy and an experimental progress in India.

References

1. Abdolmohammadi M, Howe M, Ryack K. Students' perceptions of learning in a web-assisted financial statement analysis course. *Advances in Accounting Education*. 2003;5:181-97.
2. Ambadkar R, Vyas AH, Bhargava J. Changing accounting education in India through MOOCs. *EPR International Journal of Economic and Business Review*. 2015;3(7):149-53.
3. Anderson SE, Bauman CC. Low-income taxpayer clinics as a form of service learning. *Advances in Accounting Education*. 2004;6:117-32.
4. Arquero-Montano JL, Cardoso SMJ, Joyce J. Skills development, motivation and learning in financial statement analysis: An evaluation of alternative types of case studies. *Accounting Education*. 2004;13(2):191-212.
5. Barsky NP, Catanach AH Jr. Motivating student interest in accounting: A business planning approach to the introductory management accounting course. *Advances in Accounting Education*. 2005;7:27-63.
6. Basioudis IG, De Lange PA. An assessment of the learning benefits of using a web-based learning environment when teaching accounting. *Advances in Accounting, incorporating Advances in International Accounting*. 2009;25:13-19.
7. Beaman I, Waldmann E, Krueger P. The impact of training in financial modelling principles on the incidence of spreadsheet errors. *Accounting Education*. 2005;14(2):199-212.
8. Braun RL, Simpson WR. The pause method in undergraduate auditing: An analysis of student assessments and relative effectiveness. *Advances in Accounting Education*. 2004;6:69-85.
9. Broad M, Matthews M, McDonald A. Accounting education through an online-supported virtual learning environment. *Active Learning in Higher Education*. 2004;5(2):135-51.
10. Clinton BD, Kohlmeier JM. The effects of group quizzes on performance and motivation to learn: Two experiments in cooperative learning. *Journal of Accounting Education*. 2005;23(2):96-116.
11. Crawford L, Helliard C, Monk E, Stevenson L. SCAM: Design of a learning and teaching resource. *Accounting Forum*. 2011;35:61-72.
12. Cullen J, Richardson S, O'Brien R. Exploring the teaching potential of empirically-based case studies. *Accounting Education*. 2004;13(2):251-66.
13. DeLange P, Suwardy T, Mavondo F. Integrating a virtual learning environment into an introductory accounting course: Determinants of student motivation. *Accounting Education*. 2003;12(1):1-14.
14. Dowling C, Godfrey JM, Gyles N. Do hybrid flexible delivery teaching methods improve accounting students' learning outcomes? *Accounting Education*. 2003;12(4):373-91.
15. Dunbar AE. Genesis of an online course. *Issues in Accounting Education*. 2004;19(3):321-43.
16. Green BP, Calderon TG. Assessing student learning and growth through audit risk simulations. *Advances in Accounting Education*. 2005;7:1-25.
17. Gujarathi M. Use of ERP software in accounting: A teaching note. *Advances in Accounting Education*. 2005;7:207-20.
18. Halabi AK. Accounting teleteaching lectures: Issues of interaction and performance. *Accounting Forum*. 2005;29:207-17.
19. Halabi AK, Tuovinen JE, Maxfield JL. Tele teaching accounting lectures across a multi campus: A student's perspective. *Accounting Education*. 2002;11(3):257-70.
20. Hosal-Akman N, Simga-Mukan C. An assessment of the effects of teaching methods on academic performance of students in accounting courses. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*. 2010;47(3):251-60.
21. Hwang NR, Lui G, Tong MYJ. An empirical test of cooperative learning in a passive learning environment. *Issues in Accounting Education*. 2005;20(2):151-65.
22. Klement M. Models of integration of virtualization in education: Virtualization technology and possibilities of its use in education. *Computers & Education*. 2017;105:31-43.
23. Kopel RR, Dudley LW. A beginner's guide to internet-enhanced financial accounting courses. *Advances in Accounting Education*. 2003;5:289-303.
24. Koukoulfiki S. Current trends in teaching using ICT in higher education [master's thesis]. University of Macedonia; c2009.
25. Lindquist TM, Olsen LM. How much help is too much help? An experimental investigation of the use of check figures and completed solutions in teaching intermediate accounting. *Journal of Accounting Education*. 2007;25(3):103-17.
26. Love N, Fry N. Accounting students' perceptions of a virtual learning environment: Springboard or safety net? *Accounting Education: An International Journal*. 2006:151-66.
27. Marriott N. Using computerized business simulations and spreadsheet models in accounting education: A case study. *Accounting Education*. 2004;13(Suppl. 1):55-70.
28. Marriott N, Marriott P, Selwyn N. Accounting undergraduates' changing use of ICT and their views on using the internet in higher education - A research note. *Accounting Education*. 2004;13(Suppl. 1):117-30.
29. Nouri H, Shahid A. The effect of PowerPoint presentations on student learning and attitudes. *Global Perspectives on Accounting Education*. 2005;2:53-73.
30. O'Leary R, Ramsden A. *Virtual Learning Environments, The Handbook for Economics Lecturers*; c2002.
31. Peng J. Using an online homework system to submit accounting homework: of cognitive need, computer efficacy, and perception. *Journal of Education for Business*. 2009;84(5):263-68.
32. Sidiropoulos D. Design and development of surrounding web and asynchronous distance education with the possibility of individualized learning - An application in economics [PhD dissertation]. University of Macedonia; c2008.
33. Spathis C. Use of information technologies and communication by business studies students.

- Proceedings of the 4th Conference in UTIC, Athens' University, Athens, Greece; c2004.
34. Stanley T, Edwards P. Interactive multimedia teaching of accounting information systems (AIS) cycles: Student perceptions and views. *Journal of Accounting Education*. 2005;23(1):21-46.
 35. Still K, Clayton PR. Utilizing service-learning in accounting programs. *Issues in Accounting Education*. 2004;19(4):469-486.
 36. Weil S, Oyelere P, Rainsbury E. The usefulness of case studies in developing core competencies in a professional accounting programme: A New Zealand study. *Accounting Education*. 2004;13(2):139-169.
 37. Wells P, De Lange P, Fieger P. Integrating a virtual learning environment into a second-year accounting course: Determinants of overall student perception. *Accounting and Finance*. 2008;48:503-518.
 38. Tyrovouzis P. The use of new technologies in teaching economics: The influence of the open source development model [Ph.D. dissertation]. University of Macedonia; c2006.